

The enlargement of international organisations

Veronica Anghel & Erik Jones

To cite this article: Veronica Anghel & Erik Jones (2025) The enlargement of international organisations, *West European Politics*, 48:1, 1-28, DOI: [10.1080/01402382.2024.2311044](https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2024.2311044)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2024.2311044>

© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 16 Feb 2024.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 4912

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Citing articles: 11 View citing articles [↗](#)

The enlargement of international organisations

Veronica Anghel^a

^aSchool of Advanced International Studies, Johns Hopkins University, Bologna, Italy; ^bRobert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies, European University Institute, Florence, Italy

ABSTRACT

Scholars tend to study international organisations as selective clubs. Theorising organisations as clubs, however, obscures an important aspect of their evolution that is connected to the goods they produce. Some organisations produce goods that are increasingly attractive and accessible to non-members. Those organisations face pressures to enlarge beyond the optimal size suggested by club theory, changing the experience of membership fundamentally. Over time, lower exclusivity, increased rivalry, and tighter governance structures shift the organisation from producing club-goods to managing common resource pools. The case of the European Union illustrates this transformation. By theorising the EU as a collection of common resources pools rather than a club, this study underscores how the EU accompanied the pressure for greater inclusiveness and competition for resources with reforms to strengthen member states' self-discipline and multilateral surveillance. Such institutional reforms were and remain necessary for any international organisation to avoid the tragedy of the commons.

KEYWORDS International organisations; enlargement; tragedy of the commons; club theory; European Union

At the start of the 2008 global economic and financial crisis, the worlds' wealthiest governments shifted their attention from the Group of Seven (G7) leading industrial nations to the Group of Twenty (G20). The G7 was a club that produced 'coordination' in global macroeconomic performance as a good (Putnam and Bayne 1984). As the crisis deepened, however, policy makers realised that the G7 was no longer large enough for its 'coordination' to influence global macroeconomic performance. This change in venue to the G20 was at best only partially successful. With its more heterogeneous membership, the G20 had greater difficulty coming to agreement, particularly with respect to the reduction of macroeconomic imbalances; it also experienced free-riding from those who sought to benefit from coordination without contributing through their own self-discipline (Smith 2011).

CONTACT Veronica Anghel vanghel1@jhu.edu

This article has been republished with minor changes. These changes do not impact the academic content of the article.

© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

The transition from the G7 to the G20 is not an isolated case where policymakers choose to shift from smaller to larger organisations. To unpack the rationale behind such a move, the study of selective international organisations or regional organisations typically focuses on formal membership and hence on the club-like qualities of those organisations (Davis and Wilf 2017; Hooghe *et al.* 2019; Pelle *et al.* 2021). Just like clubs, international organisations are modelled as cooperative and voluntary institutional arrangements for the provision of club goods (Buchanan 1965). The net benefits of working together on the policies governed by the club drive within-club collaboration.

From this perspective, club enlargement – moving from a smaller to a larger organisation – is a serious matter that weighs the benefits of additional membership against the costs of greater heterogeneity, the risk of free-riding, or the problem of greater congestion in decision making. That rationale is well understood both in the literature and by practitioners. Nevertheless, selective international organisations often expand for purposes other than strictly maximising members' payoffs according to a logic of consequences. Decisions concerning institutional membership can be influenced by other concerns such as normative appropriateness (Wendt 2001), geopolitics (Hofmann 2009; Simpson 2004), technological change (Viola 2020), organisational culture (Vaughan 1999; Weaver and Nelson 2016), or even competition and misperception among existing members (Gray *et al.* 2017).

What is less known is how becoming less exclusive affects the nature of the organisation itself. One possibility is that existing member states will rewrite the rules of the organisation to make it more democratic and inclusive, another is that they will rewrite the rules to restore or reinforce the privileged position of some club members. Viola (2020) contrasts the 'expansion thesis' of greater democratisation with a 'closure thesis' of reinforced privilege and hierarchy. In doing so, Viola draws attention to the 'rights' and 'roles' that international organisations create alongside substantive goods. This is an important contribution. Nevertheless, it leaves out consideration of the substantive goods that international organisations produce. As the example of the G7 and the G20 highlights, the substantive good – in that case coordination to exercise effective control over macroeconomic performance – is also important in understanding how an international organisation works.

To bridge this gap, we focus on those selective membership international organisations that produce substantive goods that cannot be contained easily by the drafting or redrafting of club rules related to the rights and roles of membership. These international organisations may have started by producing club goods, which are exclusive in nature, but

could no longer maintain that exclusive character over time. The pressure to enlarge a club's membership – which is the reverse of the ease of excluding new members – increased to a point where it became necessary to rewrite the rules not just in terms of rights and roles, but also in terms of the requirements for sustainable access to the good that is being produced. The reason for the change is that the underlying substantive good that the organisation produced had morphed into the 'common resource pools', or CRP-goods, that Ostrom (1990, 2005) studied within the tradition of new institutional economics.

What we argue – building on Ostrom (1990, 2005) – is that the pressure to enlarge, the increase of rivalry over substantive goods, and tighter governance structures indicate a shift in the nature of an international organisation from the production of club goods to the more complicated challenge of managing CRP-goods. This shift goes beyond redefining hierarchies within the club.

The policy implications of identifying selective membership organisations that administer increasingly attractive CRP-goods as opposed to club goods are profound. Specifically, all members with access to the CRP-good must exercise an ever-stronger mix of self-discipline and multilateral surveillance in the enforcement of rules of access or risk the collapse of the organisation together with the substantive good it produces.

We develop this argument in two main sections. The first section is theoretical and helps to position our contribution within the international relations literature on the expansion of international organisations. Specially, we explain how it is possible to use the insights from the economic theory of goods and theory of regional integration to suggest how a club good can evolve into a CRP-good. This combination of insights sets the scope conditions for our analysis. We are interested in those selective membership international organisations that produce substantive goods that come to share the characteristics of CRP-goods over time (and not those organisations created explicitly to manage cross-border 'common goods' – see, e.g. Heritier 2002). We argue that organisations that start by producing club goods that come to share the characteristics of CRP-goods will face increasing pressure for enlargement and increasing need to strengthen both the rules for access to the goods they produce and the enforcement of those rules through self-discipline and multilateral surveillance.

The second section introduces our case study – the European Union (EU) – to trace the evolution of three distinct substantive goods from club-goods to CRP-goods: the single market, the single currency, and the single financial space. In each case, we show the increasing difficulty that the EU faced in excluding non-members from access to European

markets, currency, and financial institutions, the increased rivalry over these three fundamental goods that the EU offers, and the promulgation of ever more elaborate frameworks for the exercise of self-discipline and multilateral surveillance in the enforcement of rules of access on existing member states. In the case of the EU, what started as a club evolved into a complex self-governing organisation for the management of common resource pools.

The conclusion pulls the theory and empirical analysis together to suggest what we might add to our understanding of international organisations and their future.

International organisations, regional integration, and the economic theory of goods

Despite great variation in explaining the origin, design, and function of international organisations, most schools of thought in international relations, from realism to constructivism, are more or less united in seeing those organisations as cooperative clubs that engage in negotiations for self-beneficial purposes that need not necessarily be material (Pevehouse and von Borzyskowski 2016). The study of international organisations has also generally converged around acknowledging greater levels of complexity by embedding them in a wider network of institutions. In this analytical space, we learn how regional organisations such as the EU influence others through diffusion (Börzel and Risse 2012), but also how they create regime complexity and interact in governing global policy issues (e.g. Alter and Meunier 2009; Eilstrup-Sangiovanni and Westerwinter 2022).

The most advanced models for analysis that perceive individual international organisations as clubs stretch to accommodate arrangements that vary from international organisations with ample size, such as the United Nations or the World Bank, to regional organisations, such as the EU or Mercosur. The goods that these organisations manage include peace keeping, international finance, the environment, health, trade, human rights, criminal justice, etc. Regional organisations are even more club-like insofar as they do not aspire to universal or encompassing membership. Instead, they should seek to achieve a kind of size-optimisation that brings them closer to how economic theory defines a ‘club’.

That normative ‘should’ does not hold in practice. Regional organisations do aspire to some level of exclusivity (Larsen 2021). Nevertheless, they create dynamics that make exclusivity hard to maintain, leading scholars to raise questions on the completeness of their club-like features (Brummer 2008; Sandler 1982). According to economic theories of integration, the goods regional organisations provide attract the attention of

non-member non-state actors like firms, NGOs, or civil society organisations (Cowles 2003; Higgott *et al.* 2000; Mattli 1999).

These non-state actors from non-member states seek to access the attractive goods that international organisations produce (Stone Sweet and Sandholtz 1998). They also seek to influence how the goods are produced and how that production is managed. This dynamic extends the reach of the organisation beyond its original member states. It also creates incentives for non-member state governments to associate with or even join the organisation so that they can gain formal access to the privileges of membership; and it creates incentives for existing member states to open their doors to new participants in order to share the costs of governance arrangements from which these non-member states already benefit through the (informal or formal) participation of non-state actors (Hofmann *et al.* 2023).

These economic theories of integration do not tell us what happens to the organisation that produces or administers such attractive goods as it becomes more open to outside actors and when it decides to enlarge. This is where we focus our attention. It is also where insights from the economic theory of clubs and goods become relevant to our research question.

The economic theory of goods encompasses a set of four ideal types constructed out of two dimensions – excludability and rivalry (or subtractability). Figure 1 shows the ideal types of goods. These goods can be excludable or not excludable, meaning it is or is not possible to prevent external actors from accessing or benefiting from the goods. Any access to the goods can be rivalrous (or subtractable), meaning one actor's consumption of the good either takes away from its availability to others or it does not (Ostrom 2005). Goods that are excludable and subtractable are private while goods that are neither excludable nor subtractable are public. The illustrations here are straightforward. A single apple is a private good because whoever has it can eat it and then no one else gets it; fresh air outdoors is a public good because someone breathing cannot stop others from breathing and yet one's breath of fresh air does not deprive anyone else from breathing.

	RIVALROUS	NON-RIVALROUS
EXCLUDABLE	Private	Club (or Toll)
NON-EXCLUDABLE	Common Resource Pool	Public

Figure 1. Ideal typical economic goods.

The mixed categories are more complicated to untangle. Goods that are excludable and yet not subtractable are club (or toll) goods; goods that are not excludable and yet subtractable are common resource pools (or CRP-goods). A classroom is an example of a club good, insofar as adding students enhances the experience only up to a certain point. By contrast, an aquifer in the desert might be a common resource pool because the people who live there need water to survive and yet the water consumed by one person is no longer available to the rest.

The traditional typology in [Figure 1](#) also suggests the governance arrangements attached to each of these goods ([Ostrom 2005](#)). The enforcement of private property rights is necessary to have private goods. A private good is excludable only because the law (or a generally accepted rule) so dictates, and it is only subtractable because whoever holds it has the chance to consume it. Similarly, public goods need to be provided by otherwise resourced entities who also defend the good against privatisation. Public goods create positive externalities from which all can benefit without detracting from someone else's ability to enjoy that good. Governance arrangements for public goods require the protection of that good against those who might find ways to restrict access and so keep the benefits to themselves. Those governance arrangements include boundary rules to define who should contribute to the production of the good and how, but those rules cannot prevent actors from benefitting from the good once it is provided.

Club goods need to be generated and efficiently managed by ensuring that the marginal benefits of club membership outweigh the marginal costs of access. This definition goes beyond identifying a club as any limited membership organisation. In addition to a selective membership, understood in this way, the club is a governance structure specifically designed to ensure a positive cost-benefit ratio for all members. As a result, the literature on club goods focuses on congestion and optimal sizing – as the good attracts traffic or the club grows, the resulting congestion lowers the relative benefits. A larger group also promotes more diversity and creates greater opportunities for free-riding ([Olson 1965](#)). Hence the club relies on boundary rules to determine who can access the good as well as who contributes to its production and how they contribute. In essence, these clubs produce three kinds of goods – the rights and roles for members (and non-members) in addition to the substantive good for which the club was created ([Viola 2020](#)).

A common resource pool needs even more stringent management to avoid exhaustion. A common resource pool is not a governance arrangement but a productive system that generates resource units (CRP-goods) that can be consumed. The system can be natural or human-made; the crucial characteristics are that the CRP-goods are essential both to those

who have access and to those who do not, and the common resource pool as a system has only limited productive capacity and so can be over-run by excessive demand. Similar to a club, the governance arrangement for a common resource pool necessarily needs to restrict access and creates three kinds of goods – rights, roles, and substantive goods. Unlike a club, however, the effort required both to exclude those who want to access the good and to control those who have access is considerably greater. The logic of collective action surrounding a common resource pool leads to over consumption by individual members and the collapse of the common resource if it is not appropriately managed. The challenge for any governance arrangement of common resource pools is to internalise negative externalities insofar as they force everyone with access to appreciate the consequences of their own actions both for themselves and for the group (Ostrom 1990, 2005).

The governance structures illustrated in [Figure 2](#) provide a useful framework for analysing international organisations in their capacity as administrators of economic ‘goods’. The governance arrangement and the ‘good’ they provide are interconnected. Our proposed functionalist detour directs attention towards the substantive goods generated by international organisations. This analytical approach focuses attention on the dynamic character of governance structures within an international organisation as they evolve in response to the nature of the goods they produce or manage. As contemporary theories of international organisations progressively delve into mapping complex interactions, the recognition of an organisation’s adaptive governance dynamics through the lens of the goods it administers assumes heightened significance.

This notion of functional adaptation is implicit in the modern debate on international organisations – not as the only source of institutional change, but as one among several. For example, scholars have analysed the connection that creates significant tension along the axis that runs diagonally from private goods to public goods. Proponents of the international economic order set up in the post-Second World War period

	RIVALROUS	NON-RIVALROUS
EXCLUDABLE	Recognition and enforcement of private property rights	Management to ensure marginal benefits outweigh marginal costs
NON-EXCLUDABLE	Organising collective action to internalise negative externalities	Organising collective action to generate positive externalities

Figure 2. Governance arrangement underlying ideal typical economic goods.

argued that the protection of private property is necessary to generate the positive externalities associated with market exchange (Ruggie 1982); critics of that arrangement have argued that such a regime is not only exclusive but also inherently inequitable (or subtractive) and posited that any such arrangement should be viewed as a form of expropriation of global economic activity to create a private good for those who are already wealthy (Prebisch 1962).

Following this line of argument, the global economy is a public good from which no country should be excluded (Myrdal 1956). Yet scholars of international organisations did not observe this kind of democratisation entailed by the progression from private goods to public goods at the global level. Instead, international organisations are seen to attempt to reinforce club-like governance arrangements in the form of selective membership groups within international organisations that preserve the power of specific countries (Pelle *et al.* 2021; Viola 2020).

This argument about the reinforcement of privilege through the formation of ‘clubs within clubs’ does not distinguish between a selective membership group that produces club goods and a selective membership group that manages common resource pools. The movement along the axis that runs diagonally from club goods to common resource pools has received considerably less (if any) attention within the scholarship that focuses on international organisations or even within the community of scholars working with the economic theory of goods. Students of economic clubs do not look at those organisations as evolving into common resource pools; their assumption is that the members will either stop any growth as the organisation approaches the optimal size or leave the club to set up a parallel organisation that offers a better cost-benefit ratio for its membership (Buchanan 1965). Students of international organisations have also provided limited attention to how organisations change after they are formed, although there is growing awareness of this topic (Pevehouse and von Borzyskowski 2016).

By tracing when an international organisation moves from producing club goods to CRP-goods, we highlight changes in the governance arrangements of selective membership international organisations as they expand.

Building on economic theories of integration and the theory of economic goods, we identify three (individually) insufficient but (collectively) necessary conditions to predict a shift from an organisation that administers or produces club goods to one that manages common resource pools:

1. The club’s *exclusivity diminishes* as outsiders access the good they produce. This insight comes from the literature on regional integration.

2. *Rivalry increases* as competition for access and influence over the good grows with more participants. This insight comes from the economic theory of goods.
3. *Governance arrangements tighten* to address issues related to heterogeneity, congestion, and free riding. This insight comes from the new institutional economics tradition.

When these three elements come together, the experience of being a member changes fundamentally because the governance arrangements impose greater responsibility for self-discipline and multilateral surveillance to protect the system that produces the underlying substantive good. The risk is not simply that some member states will lose privilege or status relative to others; it is more fundamentally functional. Where members rebel against this greater discipline, the underlying productive system – that generates CRP-goods – is vulnerable to collapse.

The next section illustrates this movement from club good to common resource pool with the example of the European Union as a selective membership organisation that produces attractive goods.

The transformation of the European community

The European Union is a common starting point in understanding the evolution of selective or regional international organisations (Haas 1961). In addition, a large body of literature has evaluated the way in which European institutional arrangements can be adopted for other regional integration projects. Features of the EU (and its predecessor organisations) have been introduced as templates for projects such as the African Union, ASEAN, and Mercosur (Börzel and Risse 2012; Dri 2010; Farrell 2007; Kim 2014; Murray and Moxon-Browne 2013).

The origins of the European Union lie in the Rome Treaty that created the common market (called the ‘single market’ after the 1987 Single European Act, and so rebranded the ‘single market’ in this paper anachronistically to make it easier to follow the historical narrative). The single market associated with the European Economic Community was a club arrangement insofar as the initial goal was to ensure that all member states benefitted, even if there were distributive consequences from membership (Ahrens, *et al.* 2005; Pelle *et al.* 2021). Consequently, the literature on European enlargement focused on implications that derive from club theory.

That research has been complicated by the fact that formal enlargement was not the only condition leading to this transformation of the EU as an organisation. The goods that the EU managed also attracted

non-member non-state actors. For example, British firms became involved in the single market long before the UK joined as a formal member. They exported and invested in Europe, built supply chains, and even began to organise to influence European regulation. In many ways, formal enlargement to the United Kingdom was a response to this penetration of European institutions and the goods they produced by actors that were not part of the original membership (Rollings 2007).

British firms were hardly alone in benefiting from European integration. Moreover, the two processes – the integration of actors from outside the European Union into the European economy and formal enlargement of membership – were mutually reinforcing. At each step in the expansion of membership, it became harder for existing members to exclude other countries from access to and influence over the goods that European institutions provide. With each expansion of access to the goods it manages, European institutions faced greater rivalry in terms of the benefits for individual member states. This rivalry was not just about market share, but also about the rules for production – product, labour, and environmental standards – that have an impact on relative cost competitiveness. The European Union became less exclusive, the membership more crowded, and access to the goods more rivalrous (or subtractive).

The challenge of European enlargement is not only a problem of member state adaptation or institutional reform. More fundamentally, it is a transformation of the ‘goods’ that the European Union provides when shifting from a club arrangement – which is exclusive and non-rivalrous – to a common resource pool arrangement – which is less exclusive and more rivalrous. To protect the way they do business, treat workers, and safeguard the environment, Europeans write rules for accessing their single market and enforce those rules – not just vis-à-vis the outside world, but also internally. As a result, members had to exercise more self-discipline and accept greater multilateral surveillance.

In order to illustrate this process, we concentrate on the evolution of three economic goods that are at the core of the European Union: the single market, the single currency, and the single financial space. These economic projects can and have been analysed as ‘club goods’ (Ahrens *et al.* 2005; Pelle *et al.* 2021). Our argument is that each of these three economic goods has evolved into a common resource pool, reinforced both by access to the good by non-state actors from outside the European Union and by successive waves of EU enlargement.

The single market: from liberalisation to rule of law

The European Economic Community that began with the Treaty of Rome in 1958 was a project of negative integration, removing tariffs and quotas

that inhibited trade and then accompanying that with the development of a common external commercial policy. This is a club-like feature. France rejected efforts to broaden the membership of the club and pushed back against efforts to shift towards more 'positive' forms of integration through the elaboration of common standards and the strengthening of internal governance arrangements (Silj 1967; Teasdale 2016). The most contentious element was the creation of a common agricultural policy, which had characteristics closer to a common resource pool that involved significant negative externalities and therefore also redistributive elements. But such tensions could be managed through the insistence on a national veto over matters of national interest through the 1965 Luxembourg compromise (Teasdale 1993).

Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of the single market as driven by key documents and moments of enlargement. The documents are important to map the evolution of the governance arrangements, which move from negative integration in the form of elimination of tariffs and quotas to more positive integration in the form of common rules and standards. As this evolution takes place, European institutions begin to strengthen requirements for self-discipline and multilateral surveillance on the part of the member states. This transformation parallels the deepening of interdependence between Europe's internal market and markets outside Europe. It also parallels the expansion of formal membership. Moreover, these processes are interconnected insofar as greater independence and a larger membership require stronger rules for managing access to the single market.

The first round of enlargement in 1973 placed immediate strains on existing governance arrangements. It also raised significant distributive conflicts among members and grievances about increasing heterogeneity and hence on the unequal access to club benefits. These were hardly the first distributive conflicts to arise. Much of the tension in the 1960s surrounding the common agricultural policy was distributive as well. But the conflicts that emerged in the 1970s were significant and they could not be resolved through the introduction of an explicitly distributive instrument in the form of regional and structural funds. Nevertheless, the members of the European community refused to abandon their club-like arrangement and embrace the more ambitious governance structures outlined in the 1976 Tindemans report (Mitchell 1976). As a result, those conflicts became an increasingly important constraint on the functioning of the institution. The British budgetary question was a major roadblock (Schramm 2023).

Further enlargement to Greece in 1981 and then Spain and Portugal five years later exacerbated these complaints and required a change in the underlying governance arrangements to accommodate greater heterogeneity and to streamline decision-making processes (Preston 1997). The shift

Figure 3. The single market.

away from a club-like arrangement begins with the 1987 Single European Act. That treaty revision made it easier for the Council of Ministers to make decisions by qualified majority, but it also created a more robust framework for setting the rules for exchange between firms seeking to access the single market (Pelkmans 1987). The addition of cohesion funds provided redistribution and aimed to ease tensions that resulted from increased rivalry. Nevertheless, these changes did not eliminate internal frictions and neither did the further enlargement of the European Union in 1995 to small, wealthy countries from the Nordic and Alpine regions that were expected to become significant new net contributors. On the contrary, the smaller countries placed new demands on the governance arrangements to enhance their transparency, pushing the EU's shift away from the light-touch characteristics of a club-like arrangement even further (Miles 1995). Austria, Finland, and Sweden also required significant optouts and added congestion to decision making.

Meanwhile, the completion of the internal market generated enthusiasm as a project and increased competition between European firms and multinationals headquartered outside Europe, and between European norms and regulations and the rules that govern production outside Europe. This sparked an important internal debate, and a 1994 European Commission White Paper, about growth, competitiveness, and employment within the internal market (European Commission 2003). That debate extended across the 1990s to focus on the negative consequences of market integration between Europe and the outside world and the need for greater adaptability to the requirements for market competition within Europe. One objective in this debate was to ensure that national and (sub-national) regional economies could adjust efficiently to macroeconomic shocks so that labour mobility across countries would not pose an undue burden on national politics. The 1997 Amsterdam Treaty even included a new Title on Employment. The result was an extension of concern for relative labour market performance that grew through the accumulation of related reform processes – starting with labour markets and extending through macroeconomic dialogue to product markets – into the Lisbon Strategy (Radaelli 2003).

The Lisbon Strategy announced in March 2000 promised to strengthen the governance relationship by adding a new open method of coordination through which national governments could share best practice while at the same time encouraging one another to focus on making consistent progress. This arrangement was meant to be light touch and to run alongside the development of broad economic policy guidelines developed to shape national economic policies in the common interest. Instead, it multiplied the number of priorities to the point that it overwhelmed the management of the internal market. By the mid-term review that coincided with the 2004 enlargement to Central and Eastern Europe, European officials worried that the whole European ‘social model’ was at stake (Kok 2004). The debate shifted to implementation and adaptation of additional rules with the emphasis moving ever more clearly to multilateral surveillance and conditionality.

At the same time, the European Commission began to push a much stronger ‘beyond the border’ agenda in trade negotiations that would extend new rules for accessing the internal market for firms (and governments) outside Europe (De Bièvre 2006; Young and Peterson 2014). It also began to use its regulatory authority internally and the attractiveness of its market externally to project regulatory requirements onto non-European firms even outside the framework of formal trade negotiations. Those outside firms would have to adopt European standards to access European markets (Damro 2012).

This shift deepened with the enlargement to Central and Eastern Europe in 2004 and 2007. The core of the formal enlargement process has always included an obligation for new members to approximate the *acquis communautaire*, or body of rules that make up the single market. For the enlargement to Central and Eastern Europe, however, the European Council established an explicit set of political criteria that extended to how the rules are made and enforced within the candidate countries (Vachudova 2005). The ‘rule of law’ could no longer be taken for granted, and so demonstration of the effectiveness of legal institutions became a major sticking point in the negotiations. It even became the justification for delaying the accession of Bulgaria and Romania, and it explains why those countries were brought in under special arrangements to ensure they continued to make progress in battling corruption and strengthening their judicial institutions (Anghel and Jones 2022).

The final turning point from the single market as a club good to a common resource pool came with the Lisbon Treaty in 2009. That treaty introduced greater protections for fundamental rights and gave the European Union full legal personality in dealing with matters of justice and home affairs. The Lisbon Treaty also made it possible for European institutions to enforce member state protection of the ‘rule of law’ in all participating countries – provisions made stronger by the elaboration of a new EU framework in 2014 (European Commission 2014). At the same time, the Treaty strengthened the abilities of the European Commission to ensure adequate protection of the environment.

Within the context of the Lisbon Treaty, the balance of attention shifted away from market liberalisation to addressing negative externalities. The single market is incompatible with a differentiated protection of the rule of law, as that leads to distortions in the protection of private property and the structure of market competition (Kelemen 2019). The difference between firms that pay the costs associated with their impact on the environment and those that don’t also distort the maintenance of the single market. The EU dealt with such distortions not only by strengthening enforcement mechanisms, but also through the creation of new opportunities for redistribution and solidarity – like the European instrument for temporary Support to mitigate Unemployment Risks in an Emergency (SURE) and Next Generation EU programs that were introduced during the Covid-19 pandemic (Buti and Fabbrini 2023). What started as a club-good moved towards a common resource pool.

The single currency: from monetary stability to macroeconomic policy coordination

A similar pattern can be found in the European project to broaden the zone of monetary stability (see Figure 4). The process started with efforts

to construct a parallel exchange rate to strengthen the functioning of price support within the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Within the Bretton Woods System, the U.S. dollar already provided monetary stability, and yet countries that participated in the CAP needed even more stability to achieve their agricultural objectives. The CAP operated on the basis of common price supports that became difficult to manage when there was volatility in the exchange rates between different currencies. The introduction of 'green currencies' helped avoid excessive bilateral fluctuations within their commitments to the dollar exchange rate standard. Member states soon realised that a broader arrangement could also support the process of trade integration within the European Common Market (McNamara 1993).

In 1970, Europeans announced their intention progressively to tighten their bilateral exchange rate fluctuations so that they could move jointly against the dollar. The Werner Plan outlined a club arrangement within the Bretton Woods System insofar as countries would coordinate their

Figure 4. The single currency.

exchange rate policies to limit exchange rate divergences within Europe. When the Bretton Woods System collapsed, and new members joined the EEC, those efforts at joint coordination took on greater imperative. The goal shifted to replace the Bretton Woods arrangement rather than improve it (Tsoukalis 1977). Their efforts at stabilising bilateral exchange rates *via* the 1972 Basel Agreement ended in failure. As the world moved towards more freely floating exchange rates, governments recognised that they would have to commit to more than just declaratory policy to produce monetary stability. That realisation, admitted in the 1975 Marjolin report, led to the creation of a more ambitious European Monetary System (EMS) in 1979 (Ludlow 1982; Marjolin 1975). This increased the size of the club again.

The EMS initially failed to stabilise exchange rates. During its first four years of operation, the exchange rate mechanism (ERM) was subject to repeated realignments. The problem remained that diverging domestic policies created powerful negative externalities for other members. The practice of competitive devaluations made that problem worse as governments took advantage of the stability already generated within the club-like arrangement by lowering the value of their domestic currency relative to the others and thereby gaining a relative cost advantage for their exports into the single market. The 1983 French government's U-turn from Keynesian demand stimulus to more austerity (known at the time as '*rigueur*') in its macroeconomic policy reflected the trade-offs entailed in seeking exchange rate stability. EU governments began to engage in concerted macroeconomic policy coordination and hardened the European Monetary System (McCarthy 1990). The shift away from a club-like arrangement to manage rivalry among members and generate stability began at this time.

The success of the EMS also attracted new participants. Italy narrowed its fluctuation bands, and the UK formally joined the Exchange Rate Mechanism. Such coordination placed increasing constraints on national governments (Giavazzi and Pagano 1988). And, while the political commitment to monetary stability found credibility in the markets, the potential for destabilising speculation against one or more currencies increased. This is an example of outside non-state actors seeking to benefit from exploiting (and undermining) the good produced by European institutions.

This potential for destabilising speculation inspired European Commission officials – led by Tomaso Padoa-Schioppa and Jacques Delors – to argue in favour of the replacement of the EMS with a single currency (Delors 1989; Padoa-Schioppa 1987). Their goal was to eliminate market speculation by irrevocably fixing exchange rates between participating countries. But monetary union required even greater commitment to reduce negative externalities related to the impact of government

spending on price inflation and so the negotiation of the Maastricht Treaty included convergence criteria that extended to the conduct of fiscal policy. Such commitments went beyond what market participants were willing to accept as credible and so they attacked the EMS in 1992 and 1993, pushing the UK out of the ERM and threatening the single currency as a project (Higgins 1993).

In response, European political leaders doubled down on the convergence requirements through the promotion of a Stability and Growth Pact, continuing the EU's shift away from a club-like arrangement (Heipertz and Verdun 2010). They also loosened the way they enforced the Exchange Rate Mechanism to make it harder for market participants – often investors located outside the European Union but trading on European currency markets – to push members out. The result had different effects on different countries. The British refused to participate in an arrangement that required so much constraint on domestic macroeconomic policy as enforced by multilateral surveillance; the Italians embraced the need for external support and self-discipline (Della Sala 1998).

Other countries – like Spain, Portugal, and Greece – saw the logic behind the joint provision of monetary stability even if this implied considerable restraints on the conduct of domestic politics. The result was again to broaden participation and so set the stage for the launch of a single currency with eleven members in 1999, adding Greece as a twelfth soon after. This success led to a broadening of monetary stability but strengthened the potential for negative externalities – particularly given that the currency area included such heterogeneous participants (Moses 2017). The implications became apparent the first time the Stability and Growth Pact was tested in 2003. The French and German governments refused to abide by the rules they had adopted and instead sought to reform the Stability and Growth Pact in 2005 to give themselves greater flexibility (Heipertz and Verdun 2010).

Such flexibility was not the solution to the problems of the euro area. Member states realised that the solution was greater macroeconomic policy coordination during the economic and financial crisis that started in the United States in 2007. This is when the shift to the single currency as a common resource pool solidified. The introduction of new regulations to reinforce the Stability and Growth Pact – the ‘Two Pack’, the ‘Six Pack’, and the ‘Fiscal Compact’ – bound national governments to a form of austerity that proved self-destructive (Moses 2017). The nature of the coordination problem that the Europeans faced derived from the behaviour of financial market participants – many of whom were located outside Europe – who had taken advantage of the creation of the single currency to diversify their holdings of cross-border investments only to unwind those positions suddenly, reversing cross border capital flows, following

the onset of the crisis (Fagan and Gaspar 2008; Merler and Pisani-Ferry 2012).

European policymakers slowly recognised this distinction between the effects of monetary integration (irrevocable fixing of exchange rates) and financial market integration (gradual development of cross-border investments followed by a sudden unwinding of accumulated positions). In response, they introduced an even greater reinforcement of the governance mechanisms and an even heavier reliance on multilateral surveillance and conditionality – which extended to include macroeconomic imbalances as well as fiscal policy. What had started as a club-good turned into a common resource pool. As a result, the debate over an effective macroeconomic governance framework has taken on existential significance for the European project (Chang 2023).

The single financial space: from mutual recognition to banking union

The evolution of European financial market integration necessarily connects the creation of the single market with the creation of the single currency. Figure 5 below shows the transition of the single financial space from a club good to a common resource pool.

The First Banking Directive in 1977 was an attempt to bring finance into the common market; the 1987 Tommaso Padoa-Schioppa Report was an argument about the need for monetary integration to run alongside the liberalisation of national capital markets (Padoa-Schioppa 1987). Nevertheless, the liberalisation of capital flows in the late 1980s was at the centre of the project to integrate national financial markets. The idea was to match the funds available in countries with surplus savings with the investment opportunities in those countries that needed capital through the creation of a single financial space. Such cross-border capital flows would increase the efficiency of European capital markets by raising the return available to savers while lowering the cost of capital for firms looking to invest in innovation, technology, or machinery (Blanchard and Giavazzi 2002). The problem policymakers faced is that capital market liberalisation is not enough to encourage cross-border capital flows (Feldstein and Horioka 1980). To achieve that outcome, it is also necessary to create the conditions for financial firms to move funds across national boundaries in the confidence that they will be able to get that money back. Exchange rate stability is one precondition; the mutual recognition of financial firms by national authorities is another.

European financial market integration started within the single market along very light-touch principles that treated banks (as firms) like any

Figure 5. The single financial space.

other tradeable goods and services (Story and Walter 1997). This led to a consolidation of banking within countries and then a surge in cross-border mergers and acquisitions both inside the EU and involving firms located outside. This combination exceeded all expectations as interest rates converged across countries within the single market; that convergence then spread to non-member countries on the borders of the single market that looked likely to join the European Union (Hoffmann 2013). Moreover, as trade became easier and exchange rates became more stable in the 1990s, this convergence of interest rates continued until the differences in borrowing costs were all but eliminated. In terms of capital market efficiency, this constituted a major success. But the benefits spread far beyond the European marketplace as non-European investors expanded their positions in European markets and European investors expanded their holdings abroad (Mügge 2010).

By the start of the 2000s, European policy makers began to realise that the growth of financial institutions in Europe had begun to create problems for national regulatory oversight – particularly as countries managed to integrate with European financial markets even though they did not

belong to the single market or have any prospect of joining the single currency (Mügge 2010). Europe's financial club found it difficult to exclude non-members from the benefits of membership. They also began to realise that financial stability no longer focused only on individual financial institutions – micro-prudential risk – but also took on systemic properties as large financial institutions became dependent upon one another both inside and outside Europe. This was not a new realisation. The globalisation of finance started already in the 1970s – around the time of the First Banking Directive – and financial market regulators began coordinating across countries then as well (Story and Walter 1997). Nevertheless, the level of concern and the need for greater coordination was much greater than in the past. Therefore, policymakers looked for ways to promote industry self-regulation – relying on what came to be known as the Lamfalussy process (Lamfalussy 2001).

The introduction of this process started a shift away from the EU as a club-like arrangement in this area of observation as well. At the same time, however, the Lamfalussy process strengthened the competitive position of the largest cross-border banks while weakening the oversight of national regulatory authorities (Posner 2007). This was true particularly in Central and Eastern Europe, where large West European banks assumed an outsized role in providing financial services (Epstein 2017).

The global economic and financial crisis that began in 2007 revealed the weakness of European financial market regulation. It also triggered a sudden reversal of many years of cross-border investments. This reversal is what created turbulence in sovereign debt markets as a major negative externality (Merler and Pisani-Ferry 2012). The policy response was to promote a more centralised form of financial market regulation through the creation of European financial regulatory authorities (De Larosière 2009). It was also to negotiate with West European banks to ensure that they would not abandon Central and East European markets (Epstein 2017). This combination of factors completed the shift away from the single financial space being a club good to becoming a common resource pool.

Nevertheless, that response proved inadequate to stabilise either the banks or sovereign debt markets. Ultimately both Spain and Italy looked likely to collapse, implicating both their financial systems and their public finances (Van Rompuy 2014). The collapse of those countries, however, could not be contained within their national boundaries. Both the single European financial space and the single currency were at risk. The only solution was for the European Central Bank (ECB) to step in as lender of last resort. To do so, however, the ECB required the creation of a much stronger single supervisory mechanism to oversee systemically significant financial institutions and a common rulebook for financial oversight.

Powerful member states, like Germany, insisted on such provisions as well. European policymakers also agreed to the creation of a permanent bailout authority in the form of the European Stability Mechanism and promised to move towards a fully articulated 'banking union' (Howarth and Quaglia 2016; Juncker *et al.* 2015).

Tracing the shift of the single financial space from a club-good to a common resource pool shows that the stability of the European project hinges critically on its ability to manage the negative externalities associated with the behaviour of its many financial market participants – meaning both state actors and non-state actors alike. In turn, these actors require greater self-discipline and more extensive multilateral surveillance.

Three dimensions, one pattern

The European single market, single currency, and single financial space no longer operate as club goods with light-touch governance arrangements to ensure each member state enjoys net benefits. Instead, the governance arrangements focus on procedures to protect the rule of law, ensure the effective coordination of macroeconomic policies, and underpin (and enforce) financial stability. Those procedures have developed in response to the progressively greater heterogeneity of member states. They focus on the prevention of free riding. And they also suffer from problems associated with congestion in terms of decision making. That is why the enforcement provisions of the new framework for protection of the rule of law are found wanting (Södersten 2023), the framework for macroeconomic policy coordination remains controversial (Buti and Fabbri 2023), and the banking union remains incomplete (Pierret and Howarth 2023).

Meanwhile, the pressure for further enlargement continues to increase to include non-members who are already benefiting from access to multiple attractive EU goods. Hence, the European Union has embarked on a new and ambitious project of enlargement to countries in Eastern Europe and in the Western Balkans (European Council 2022). Those countries will add to heterogeneity, congestion, and the risk of free riding in one or more key areas related to the protection of the rule of law, the maintenance of sound macroeconomic policies, and the preservation of financial stability (Anghel and Džankić 2023). But such concerns are balanced against the imperative of access for reasons that go beyond economics. The EU is no longer a club, but an administrator of common resource pools. As a self-governing collective of common resource pools, the EU provides essential goods. According to the theory of economic goods, the challenge is to ensure that the regional organisation governs those goods in a way that does not lead to their exhaustion.

Conclusion

This article shows how international organisations avoid the tragedy of the commons. It contributes to the study of selective membership organisations by combining insights from theories of integration and economic goods. We argue that, while the modelling of international organisations as clubs sheds important light on how those organisations work, it fails to explain what happens when the goods they provide become attractive and accessible to non-members, when membership increases, and when the consumption of a good by any one member begins to compete with the access to that good (or the successful production of the good) for all the rest. We show that, over time, lower exclusivity, increased rivalry, and tighter governance structures shift the nature of the organisation from producing club-goods to managing common resource pools. The experience of membership changes fundamentally as a result.

A club places few requirements on its members beyond making the necessary contributions to running costs and respect for the basic rules for interaction. The governance arrangements of a club are relatively unobtrusive and focus on ensuring that the benefits outweigh the costs for all participants. By contrast, the governance arrangements for common resource pools place restraints on members in relation to their access to the underlying good. Participating in the management of common resource pools also requires members to enforce those restraints both on themselves and among one another. Finally, the governance requirements are heavier insofar as they involve close monitoring of all common pool resources and frequent adjustments of the restraints on access in line with the sustainability of the whole arrangement.

We illustrate the shift of a selective membership organisation from producing club-goods to managing common resource pools with the example of the European Union. Like any other administrator of common resource pools, the EU has developed into an arrangement where access is imperative and resource sharing is hard to govern. Future research could extend this argument to address questions that our case selection does not answer. The EU is an advanced integrated regional organisation that offers and administers multiple attractive goods. The question remains whether other selective membership organisations that are much more limited in scope necessarily follow the same evolution. In addition, our analysis looked at the evolution of fundamental economic goods such as the single market, the single currency, and the single financial space; more empirical research is necessary to trace the evolution of other selective membership organisations through the non-economic goods that they administer.

This study also has important policy implications. Many selective membership organisations deal with the consequences of expansion and

the pressure to produce and administer goods. The G20, the BRICs, the Arab League, or Mercosur, are faced with decisions to organise their governance structures and collectively administer joint resources. As the European Union gestures once more towards enlargement in the context of the Russia-Ukraine war, the implications of this argument are also significant for the development of our case study. Understood not as a club but as an organised system of common resource pools, the EU remains challenged to accompany the pressure to enlarge with internal reforms to strengthen both self-discipline and multilateral surveillance among the member states. This is true particularly in the context of rule of law and market competition, but it also applies for macroeconomic policy coordination, and financial market integration. Such institutional reforms were and remain necessary for any international organisation to avoid the depletion of the common resource pools that it manages.

Acknowledgements

West European Politics provided the best reviewers any author needs. This argument benefited hugely from the major revisions they required. We are also grateful for comments received during presentations at the 2023 annual conferences of the Midwest Political Science Association (MPSA), the Council for European Studies (CES), the American Political Science Association (APSA), and the International Relations Working Group of the European University Institute (IRWG EUI). We have greatly benefited from extensive feedback and support provided by Waltraud Schelkle, Craig Parsons, Orfeo Fioretos, Jonathan Moses, Amy Kreppel, Desmond King, Bent Sofus Tranøy, Ingrid Hjertaker, and Giorgio Giamberini.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101079219.

Notes on contributors

Veronica Anghel is a Lecturer at the Johns Hopkins School of Advanced International Studies and Visiting Fellow at the Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies at the European University Institute. Her research focuses on European integration and democracy building and has been published in *Political Communication*, the *Journal of European Public Policy*, and the *European Journal of Political Research*. [vanghell@jhu.edu]

Erik Jones is Director of the Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies at the European University Institute. He specialises in European integration and international political economy, and his work has appeared in *Comparative Political Studies* and *International Affairs* amongst others. [erik.jones@eui.eu]

ORCID

Veronica Anghel <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2499-1035>

Erik Jones <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6473-7680>

References

- Ahrens, Joachim, Herman W. Hoen, and Renate Ohr (2005). 'Deepening Integration in an Enlarged EU: A Club-Theoretical Perspective', *Journal of European Integration*, 27:4, 417–39.
- Alter, Karen J., and Sophie Meunier (2009). 'The Politics of International Regime Complexity', *Perspectives on Politics*, 7:1, 13–24.
- Anghel, Veronica, and Erik Jones (2022). 'Failing Forward in Eastern Enlargement: Problem Solving through Problem Making', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 29:7, 1092–111.
- Anghel, Veronica, and Jelena Džankić (2023). 'Wartime EU: Consequences of the Russia – Ukraine War on the Enlargement Process', *Journal of European Integration*, 45:3, 487–501.
- Blanchard, Olivier, and Francesco Giavazzi (2002). 'Current Account Deficits in the Euro Area: The End of the Feldstein-Horioka Puzzle?', *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 2002:2, 147–209.
- Börzel, Tanja, and Thomas Risse (2012). 'From Europeanisation to Diffusion: Introduction', *West European Politics*, 35:1, 1–19.
- Brummer, Chris (2008). 'Regional Integration and Incomplete Club Goods: A Trade Perspective', *Chicago Journal of International Law*, 8:2, 535–51.
- Buchanan, James M. (1965). 'An Economic Theory of Clubs', *Economica*, 32:125, 1–14.
- Buti, Marco, and Sergio Fabbrini (2023). 'Next Generation EU and the Future of Economic Governance: Towards a Paradigm Change or Just a Big One-Off?', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 30:4, 676–95.
- Chang, Michele (2023). 'Economic Governance', in Erik Jones and Masha Hedberg (eds.), *Europe Today: A Twenty-First Century Introduction*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 301–24.
- Cowles, Maria Green (2003). 'Non-State Actors and False Dichotomies: Reviewing IR/IPE Approaches to European Integration', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 10:1, 102–20.
- Damro, Chad (2012). 'Market Power Europe', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 19:5, 682–99.
- Davis, Christina, and Meredith Wilf (2017). 'Joining the Club: Accession to the GATT/WTO', *Journal of Politics*, 79:3, 964–78.
- De Bièvre, Dirk (2006). 'The EU Regulatory Trade Agenda and the Quest for WTO Enforcement', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 13:6, 851–66.
- De Larosière, Jacques (2009). *The High-Level Group of Financial Supervision in the EU*. Brussels: European Commission.

- Della Sala, Vincent (1998). 'Hollowing out and Hardening the State: European Integration and the Italian Economy', *West European Politics*, 20:1, 14–33.
- Delors, Jacques (1989). 'Report on Economic and Monetary Union in the European Community', Brussels: European Commission, April.
- Dri, Clarissa F. (2010). 'Limits of the Institutional Mimesis of the European Union: The Case of the Mercosur Parliament', *Latin American Policy*, 1:1, 52–74.
- Eilstrup-Sangiovanni, Mette, and Oliver Westerwinter (2022). 'The Global Governance Complexity Cube: Varieties of Institutional Complexity in Global Governance', *The Review of International Organizations*, 17:2, 233–62.
- Epstein, Rachel A. (2017). *Banking on Markets: The Transformation of Bank-State Ties in Europe & Beyond*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- European Commission (2003). *Growth, Competitiveness, Employment: The Challenges and Ways Forward in the 21st Century – White Paper*. Brussels: European Commission.
- European Commission (2014). 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: A New EU Framework to Strengthen the Rule of Law', Brussels: European Commission, COM(2014) 158 final.
- European Council (2022). 'European Council Conclusions on Ukraine, the Membership Applications of Ukraine, the Republic of Moldova and Georgia, Western Balkans and External Relations', Brussels: European Council, 23 June.
- Fagan, Gabriel, and Vitor Gaspar (2008). 'Macroeconomic Adjustment to Monetary Union', ECB Working Paper No. 946. Frankfurt: European Central Bank (October).
- Farrell, Mary (2007). 'From EU Model to External Policy? Promoting Regional Integration in the Rest of the World', in Sophie Meunier and Kathleen R. McNamara (eds.), *Making History: European Integration and Institutional Change at Fifty*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 299–315.
- Feldstein, Martin, and Charles Horioka (1980). 'Domestic Saving and International Capital Flows', *The Economic Journal*, 90:358, 314–29.
- Giavazzi, Francesco, and Marco Pagano (1988). 'The Advantages of Tying One's Hands: EMS Discipline and Central Bank Credibility', *European Economic Review*, 32:5, 1055–75.
- Gray, Julia, René Lindstädt, and Jonathan B. Slapin (2017). 'The Dynamics of Enlargement in International Organizations', *International Interactions*, 43:4, 619–42.
- Haas, Ernst B. (1961). 'Regional Integration: The European and the Universal Process', *International Organization*, 15:3, 366–92.
- Heipertz, Martin, and Amy Verdun (2010). *Ruling Europe: The Politics of the Stability and Growth Pact*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Heritier, Adrienne, ed. (2002). *Common Goods: Reinventing European and International Governance*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Higgins, Byron (1993). 'Was the ERM Crisis Inevitable?', *Economic Review*, 78:4, 27–40.
- Higgott, Richard A., Geoffrey R. D. Underhill, and Andreas Bieler, eds. (2000). *Non-State Actors and Authority in the Global System*. London: Routledge.
- Hoffmann, Andreas (2013). 'Carry Trades and Speculative Manias: Evidence from Central and Eastern Europe', *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 36:1, 15–30.
- Hofmann, Stephanie C. (2009). 'Overlapping Institutions in the Realm of International Security: The Case of NATO and ESDP', *Perspectives on Politics*, 7:1, 45–52.
- Hofmann, Stephanie C., Anamarija Andreska, Erna Burai, and Juanita Uribe (2023). 'Porous Organizational Boundaries and Associated States: Introducing

- Membership in International Organizations', *European Journal of International Relations*, 29:4, 929–59.
- Hooghe, Liesbet, Tobias Lenz, and Gary Marks (2019). *A Theory of International Organization*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Howarth, David, and Lucia Quaglia (2016). *The Political Economy of European Banking Union*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Juncker, Jean-Claude *et al.* (2015). *Completing Europe's Economic and Monetary Union*. Brussels: European Commission.
- Kelemen, R. Daniel (2019). 'Is Differentiation Possible in Rule of Law?', *Comparative European Politics*, 17:2, 246–60.
- Kim, Min-hyung (2014). 'Integration Theory and ASEAN', *Pacific Focus*, 29:3, 374–94.
- Kok, Wim (2004). *Facing the Challenge: The Lisbon Strategy for Growth and Employment*. Brussels: European Commission, November.
- Lamfalussy, Alexandre (2001). 'Final Report of the Committee of Wise Men on the Regulation of European Securities Markets', Brussels: European Commission.
- Larsen, Signe Rehling (2021). *The Constitutional Theory of the Federation of the European Union*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ludlow, Peter (1982). *The Making of the European Monetary System: A Case Study in the Politics of the European Community*. London: Butterworths Scientific.
- Marjolin, Robert (1975). *Report of the Study Group 'Economic and Monetary Union 1980'*. Brussels: Commission of the European Communities.
- Mattli, Walter (1999). *The Logic of Regional Integration*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- McCarthy, Patrick (1990). 'France Faces Reality: *Rigueur* and the Germans', in David P. Calleo and Claudia Morgenstern (eds.), *Recasting Europe's Economies: National Strategies in the 1980s*. Lanham: University Press of America, 25–78.
- McNamara, Kathleen R. (1993). 'Common Markets, Uncommon Currencies: System Effects and the European Community', in Jack Snyder and Robert Jervis (eds.), *Coping with Complexity in the International System*. Boulder: Westview, 303–27.
- Merler, Silvia, and Jean Pisani-Ferry (2012). 'Sudden Stops in the Euro Area', Bruegel Policy Contribution, Issue 2012/06. Brussels: Bruegel (March).
- Miles, Lee (1995). 'Enlargement of the European Union and the Nordic Model', *Journal of European Integration*, 19:1, 43–69.
- Mitchell, J. D. B. (1976). 'The Tindemans Report, Retrospect and Prospect', *Common Market Law Review*, 13:4, 455–84.
- Moses, Jonathon (2017). *Eurobondage: The Political Costs of Monetary Union in Europe*. Colchester: ECPR Press.
- Mügge, Daniel (2010). *Widen the Market, Narrow the Competition: Banker Interests and the Making of a European Capital Market*. Colchester: ECPR Press.
- Murray, Philomena, and Edward Moxon-Browne (2013). 'The European Union as a Template for Regional Integration? The Case of ASEAN and Its Committee of Permanent Representatives', *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 51:3, 522–37.
- Myrdal, Gunnar (1956). *An International Economy: Problems and Prospects*. New York: Harper & Brothers.
- Olson, Mancur (1965). *The Logic of Collective Action: Public Goods and the Theory of Groups*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Ostrom, Elinor (1990). *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Ostrom, Elinor (2005). *Understanding Institutional Diversity*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Padoa-Schioppa, Tomaso (1987). *Efficiency, Stability and Equity: A Strategy for the Evolution of the Economic System of the European Community*. Brussels: Commission of the European Communities, II/49/87 (April).
- Pelkmans, Jacques (1987). 'The New Approach to Technical Harmonization and Standardization', *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 25:3, 249–69.
- Pelle, Anita, András London, and Éva Kuruczleki (2021). 'The European Union: A Dynamic Complex System of Clubs Comprised by Countries Performing a Variety of Capitalism', *Forum for Social Economics*, 50:4, 530–52.
- Pevehouse, Jon C. W., and Inken von Borzyskowski (2016). 'International Organizations in World Politics', in Jacob Katz Cogan, Ian Hurd, and Ian Johnstone (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of International Organizations*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 3–32.
- Pierret, Laura, and David Howarth (2023). 'Moral Hazard, Central Bankers, and Banking Union: Profession Dissensus and the Politics of European Financial Stability', *Journal of European Integration*, 45:1, 15–41.
- Posner, Elliot (2007). 'Financial Transformation in the European Union', in Sophie Meunier and Kathleen R. McNamara (eds.), *Making History: European Integration and Institutional Change at Fifty*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 139–58.
- Prebisch, Raúl (1962). 'The Economic Development of Latin America and Its Principal Problems', *Economic Bulletin for Latin America*, 7:1, 1–22.
- Preston, Christopher (1997). *Enlargement and Integration in the European Union*. London: Routledge.
- Putnam, Robert D., and Nicholas Bayne (1984). *Hanging Together: The Seven-Power Summits*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Radaelli, Claudio (2003). *The Open Method of Coordination: A New Governance Architecture for the European Union?* Stockholm: Swedish Institute for European Policy Studies.
- Rollings, Niel (2007). *British Business in the Formative Years of European Integration, 1945-1973*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ruggie, John Gerard (1982). 'International Regimes, Transactions, and Change: Embedded Liberalism in the Postwar Economic Order', *International Organization*, 36:2, 379–415.
- Sandler, Todd (1982). 'A Theory of Intergenerational Clubs', *Economic Inquiry*, 20:2, 191–208.
- Schramm, Lucas (2023). 'Using Go-It-Alone Power to Overcome Intergovernmental Deadlock: National Vetoes, Credible Threats, and Multi-Speed Europe in the British Budgetary Rebate Crisis', *Acta Politica*.
- Silj, Alessandro (1967). 'Europe's Political Puzzle: A Study of the Fouchet Negotiations and the 1963 Veto', Occasional Papers in International Affairs No. 17. Cambridge: Harvard Center for International Affairs.
- Simpson, Gerry (2004). *Great Powers and Outlaw States: Unequal Sovereigns in the International Legal Order*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Smith, Gordon S. (2011). 'G7 to G8 to G20: Evolution in Global Governance', CIGI G20 Papers, No. 6. Waterloo, Canada: Centre for International Governance Innovation.
- Södersten, Anna (2023). 'Rule of Law Crisis: EU in Limbo between Federalism and Flexible Integration', in Antonina Bakardjieva Engelbrekt, Per Ekman, Anna Michalska, and Lars Oxelheim (eds.), *The EU between Federal Union and Flexible Integration*. London: Palgrave, 51–74.

- Stone Sweet, Alec, and Wayne Sandholtz (1998). 'Integration, Supranational Governance, and the Institutionalization of the European Polity', in Wayne Sandholtz and Alec Stone Sweet (eds.), *European Integration and Supranational Governance*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1–26.
- Story, Jonathan, and Ingo Walter (1997). *Political Economy of Financial Integration in Europe: The Battle of the Systems*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Teasdale, Anthony L. (1993). 'The Life and Death of the Luxembourg Compromise', *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 31:4, 567–79.
- Teasdale, Anthony L. (2016). 'The Fouchet Plan: De Gaulle's Intergovernmental Design for Europe', LSE 'Europe in Question' Discussion Paper Series 117 (October).
- Tsoukalis, Loukas (1977). *The Politics and Economics of European Monetary Integration*. London: Routledge.
- Vachudova, Milada A. (2005). *Europe Undivided: Democracy, Leverage, and Integration after Communism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Van Rompuy, Herman (2014). *Europa in de Storm*. Leuven: Davidsfonds.
- Vaughan, Diane (1999). 'The Dark Side of Organizations: Mistake, Misconduct, and Disaster', *Annual Review of Sociology*, 25:1, 271–305.
- Viola, Lora Anne (2020). *The Closure of the International System: How Institutions Create Political Equalities and Hierarchies*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Weaver, Catherine, and Stephen C. Nelson (2016). 'Organizational Culture', in Jacob Katz Cogan, Ian Hurd, and Ian Johnstone (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of International Organizations*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 920–40.
- Wendt, Alexander (2001). 'Driving with the Rearview Mirror: On the Rational Science of Institutional Design', *International Organization*, 55:4, 1019–49.
- Young, Alasdair R., and John Peterson (2014). *Parochial Global Europe: 21st Century Trade Politics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.